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Manipulation of people's mind through digitalization: Ethic vs Profit

Abstract: Digitalization has become a sophisticated medium of daily activities in recent days. The issue with digitalization has created an avenue of debatable topic between ethics versus profit. Although digitalization is making life easier, it is also simultaneously manipulating peoples mind towards profit maximization objective rather than becoming socially responsible considering the ethical practices. This study explores whether technology is manipulating human behavior and if ethical practices are being applied. Interview technique was applied to collect data. Altogether 10 respondents were interviewed among these, 5 were the developers and 5 were the users. Coding was applied and data triangulation method was used for analysis. The results suggest that there are multiple ways to attract and divert peoples mind through internet web designing that developers invent to manipulate the viewers. Artificial intelligence and Internet technologies have developed a method of deep faking to manipulate people's minds. The findings suggest that manipulative features are added for pursuing people's behaviours. These manipulative features forcibly attract the users to unknowingly use the application program even if the users do not wish to. Most developers feel that ethical practices need to be maintained towards safeguarding the privacy of people and information, however, the practice of designing triggers towards manipulation. Manipulation of peoples mind are programmed and designed by managerial implicative objective of organization to gain more profit over offering ethical practices.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, well-being, technologies, managerial strategies, awareness, intelligent system, social media

Introduction

Our world has all been digitalized, creating an ever-expanding digital world of data. Digitization has led to a thriving information economy. Data is valuable because it makes it possible to make better decisions, such as which consumers should see which advertisements or which individuals should be looked into as potential scammers. In today's digital world, advertisers have grasped the chance to customize and target advertisements by using online data about customers. Such information may include the websites visited,

articles read, and videos viewed, as well as all search terms entered into search engines. This phenomenon is called online behavioral advertising (Boerman, Sanne & Frederik, 2017).

Manipulation of people's mind are a preconditional design that most companies are attracted to gain profit. However, with the momentum of gaining profit, some companies do not always practice the ethical ways. As a preconditional design, it is a method of influencing preferences through a means of cognitive balance (Izuma and Adolphs, 2013).

In this digital world, processed and analyzed data serves as the foundation for both human and automated decision-making processes that ultimately affect the physical world. We use digital technology more frequently and are relying on them more and more for all types of necessities, whether it is for banking, media, education, healthcare, or the legal system. This way the digitalization technologies is already manipulating the people's mind by making the digital technologies as a compulsion means to undertake any activities. The question arises the issue of being completely dependable in technologies nowadays. However, most people do not understand who actually benefits from the use of digital technologies. Moreover, people also have a tendency to ignore the facts about data privacy (Gerhart, 2017).

Big data advancements and intelligent algorithms based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) are essential components of the technology. These developments, for example, play a role with Internet of Things (IoT) devices that send information to the cloud (big data) and are at the same time steered by data and algorithms from the cloud to perform a specific action in the physical world (Royakkers and Timmer, 2018). In some areas, smart algorithms and intelligent systems are already taking over decision-making from people, for example, with armed drones, or in smart cars, this has further manipulated the mind of people to demand for more hi-tech equipment's for their daily uses also such as Google home, Alexa. Technologies, embedded in advisory apps on our smartphone or in smart street lights, can be persuasive and may influence our behavior and autonomy towards manipulation of mind in subtle ways.

AI technologies are progressively being used in nearly all industries and are consequently making their way into many aspects of our daily lives as a result of expanding processing power and the availability of extensive, high-quality datasets. However, the application of AI-based algorithmic systems raises ethical concerns, challenges society norms, and puts into question numerous core principles (Dignum, 2018). This relates to issues like fairness and discrimination, privacy and human autonomy in semi-automated decision-making, risks of personal and societal surveillance, and threats to democracy posed by social media misinformation and threats to human life posed by autonomous weapon systems or drones (Mittelstadt et al., 2016).

Dark patterns are user interfaces that purposefully mislead users, make it difficult for users to communicate their true preferences, or manipulate users into acting in a certain way (Jamie, Lior Jacob, 2021). Such interface design is an increasingly common occurrence on digital platforms including social media websites, shopping websites, mobile apps, and video games. They can mislead and deceive users, by causing financial loss, tricking users into giving up vast amounts of personal data, or inducing compulsive and addictive

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behavior in adults and children, this accounts for profit motives of an organization while ignoring the ethical practices by creating addictive and impulsive ways towards attractions.

Digitalization offers many benefits, including greater access to information, improved communication, and enhanced efficiency. On the other hand, there are concerns that digital platforms are being used to manipulate people's behavior and beliefs, often for commercial gain. This issue raises important ethical questions about the responsibilities of technology companies and the need to balance profit with the protection of people's rights and wellbeing. Trittin-Ulbrich et al., (2021) states that contribution of digitalization are designed for social benefit however there are negative consequences for the use of business growth, culture and political reasons. Therefore the purpose of this study is to explore the development of digitalization on manipulating people's minds for generating profits and maintaining ethical considerations towards the users.

Research Questions

1. How is digitalization manipulating people's minds?
2. How is modern digital technologies implying ethics in operational applications?
3. What are the implication of AI developed for profit or ethic?

Problem Statement

Individuals are losing control over their personal information as they unknowingly give permission to companies and organizations to collect, store, and use it when they use digital services. Most people are dragged into this unknowingly assuming every digitization activities are truth/fact which may not always be the same. People check their devices frequently because of pings, pop-ups, notifications. Once you've been interrupted, it takes several minutes to get back into the flow, so even just "one small look" can have significant effects on our ability to concentrate. Likewise, many people are not aware of their loss of privacy as they normally do not read the terms of usage. Moreover, manipulation of people's minds is instigated by the profit that organizations make, however, ethics in this connection are not completely taken into consideration. Although business ethics are primarily a concern to protect consumer's rights, it is not being implied as a norms, rights and responsibilities.

Literature review

This section review literature in technological advancement through digitalization and its features of manipulation peoples mind. The section has been segregated into different sub-titles to make it easier for the readers to understand the different views offered from various related studies.

Digitalization for individual conveniences

Digitalization refers to the process of transforming a business model through the use of digital technologies, which offers new opportunities for generating revenue and value. It involves three key elements: sensors,

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devices that enable smart systems, and connectivity integration that links these devices to the computer and digital platforms. When combined, these three elements allow for the use of predictive and prescriptive analytics, which can provide effective solutions for businesses and generate value (Porter and Heppelmann, 2014). Digitalization is also defined as the integration of technology, business models, data, and information in the creation of products, services, and processes (Passi, 2017). This can lead to innovative digital solutions through the use of new technologies. However, the moral and ethical implications of significant technological advancements are not always considered. Royakkers et al. (2018) found that digitalization had various social and ethical implications, including privacy, autonomy, safety and security, balance of power, human dignity, and justice. These themes emerged as a result of the impact of digitalization.

The collection and utilization of data is driving innovation and the development of new business models (Acquisti, 2014). Techniques such as geolocation and social media tracking are being used to customize and streamline operations (Kosinski et al., 2013). Private companies and government entities are driving the digitalization trend, which has both micro and macro-level effects. People are becoming increasingly concerned about how their personal data is collected and stored, resulting in the creation of privacy-focused services and regulations (Bogusz, 2019). Digital tools and data are also influencing individual behaviors and societal norms, such as addiction to computer games and changes in online and offline behavior due to surveillance technologies. The impact of digitalization extends beyond individuals to society as a whole, the environment, and issues of equity. Makinen and Junnila (2023) mentions data surveillance must be for the benefit of society rather than for the purpose of business gain.

Digitalization manipulation and awareness

The concept of manipulation refers to covert influence, which can be interpreted as deceptive or involving cunning and subterfuge. This type of hidden influence can be observed in interpersonal interactions and is increasingly present in interactions with intelligent technologies, both online and offline (Floridi, 2014). This critical perspective on human-machine interactions is part of a broader trend that identifies techno-social engineering as a problematic process in which technologies and social forces combine to influence our thoughts, perceptions, behavior, and actions in potentially concerning ways (Klenk, 2021). Successful manipulation depends on identifying and exploiting people's decision-making weaknesses, similar to coercive tactics. Manipulation violates morality because it disregards people's autonomy by withholding information and preventing them from making decisions that align with their values and beliefs. Such deceptive online behaviors also violate the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for transparency and fairness since users are not adequately informed about the collection and processing of their data (Boynton and Portnoy, 2013).

Deceptive practices used in online businesses are becoming more apparent. Because of information technology, these practices can be used effectively and cheaply on a wide scale, in various contexts, and with great sophistication. The goal of such tactics is to influence users to make purchases, prolong their usage of a service, and convince them to accept privacy-intrusive features. This results in the infringement of user's rights to the protection of their personal data and exposes them to privacy risks. Online manipulation

disregards legal protections and deprives uninformed individuals of their capacity to make independent decisions (Bongard-Blanchy, 2021).

Manipulation methods have the power to alter people's decisions, behavior, and eventually the behavior of the society made up of these individuals by undermining their autonomy through covert manipulative strategies (Botes, 2022). Example: advertising a product, but emphasizing the scarcity of the product, which prompts the consumer to make a rapid decision based on that assumption, while otherwise the consumer could have taken more time to explore his or her options without the pressure of the product's alleged scarcity. Although the person is unable to determine the actual quantity of products that are available, proving the covert nature of manipulation, the person is nevertheless able to weigh his options in light of the information presented with respect to the product, albeit under time pressure, which may be exploiting individual weaknesses.

Ethics in Digitalization

The ethical principle of autonomy is based on the idea that human beings should always be treated as individuals with inherent worth and dignity, rather than simply as resources to be exploited (Botes, 2022). In practice, this means respecting people's rights and choices. However, in our increasingly digitized world, it can be difficult to determine what autonomy truly means and how manipulative techniques can interfere with people's decision-making processes.

Manipulative technologies can change the way people perceive certain situations and influence their beliefs, ultimately affecting the choices they make. If this process occurs without people's awareness, they are being controlled by these technologies and used for their own ends, rather than being respected as autonomous individuals. The integration of technology into society creates a situation where manipulative individuals can erode people's autonomy and control over their decision-making process (Klenk, and Hancock, 2019).

Individualized customer information is crucial to the success of online commerce. By collecting and analyzing customer data, companies can gain valuable insights into their customers' preferences and behavior, which can help them to personalize their marketing and improve the customer experience (Sarathy, Robertson, 2003). However, the collection and use of such data can also raise concerns about digital privacy. Consumers are increasingly aware of the potential risks associated with sharing personal information online, such as identity theft, data breaches, and other forms of cybercrime. This has led to a growing demand for greater transparency and control over how personal data is collected, stored, and used by businesses.

Ethic vs. Profit

Some technologies, which initially aimed to persuade people toward better lives and futures, unwittingly changed into manipulative technologies that are used to satisfy the intentions of their coders and other relevant stakeholders, even though those intentions may not be in line with the values and beliefs of the people these technologies are targeting. However, the line between manipulation and persuasion is frequently fuzzy and unclear (Botes, 2022). The proliferation of manipulative technologies has been exacerbated by the

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prevalent ethic vs. profit viewpoint, wherein pursuing the goal of financial gain often takes prominence over principles of ethics. Despite the fact that there are enough ethical principles in place to protect people from manipulative technologies, a thorough analysis of the components of these ethical principles is still lacking (Botes, 2022).

Since the beginning of the Internet, people have been trying to make money from online users, using various marketing techniques such as online sales and advertising. Digital marketing has expanded to include methods such as email, SMS, and web advertising, but the question remains about what types of marketing techniques are ethical or immoral online (Gautam, 2014). While standard advertisements are commonly used, some methods, such as pop-up ads that cover the whole screen, cookies that track users' behavior on websites, and spam emails, may not be considered ethical. Digital marketing that is consent-based can be effective as it considers the needs and interests of the consumer, but if the consumer is uninterested, the advertisements may not be effective (Rowley, 2001).

Diversion of people's mind through digital techniques

The phenomena of social media instructions, diverting concentration out of the task at the moment and in the direction of social media is social media distraction. Both internal and external stimuli may be present (Wilmer et al., 2017). The distraction can come from outside influences such as receiving notification or from within oneself when the user begins thinking about social media, such as unanswered messages. When people are working on a task, pensive thinking might cause internal distraction. As an example, prior research showed that while learning via the internet, students' thoughts frequently turned to social media (Hollis and Was, 2016).

Rather than letting people make judgments when they are relaxed, composed, and at their best, certain algorithms are intentionally created to target consumer vulnerabilities and actively direct their attention to specific aims (Kant, 1996). Current research has started to look at how technology can limit users' autonomy. For instance, a lot of online games and platforms are made to elicit a dopamine reaction in consumers that keeps them coming back for more. Games and social media products drive users to seek the positive feedback from the engagement to the point where their lives might be disturbed. Technology companies create a vulnerable consumer by using addictive design patterns (Brenkert 1998). Addictive design threatens consumers' autonomy by manipulating them and taking advantage of their behaviors.

The covert or concealed nature of manipulative practices, which try to convince or influence people against their inherent values and beliefs, is what explicitly links manipulation and autonomy. Pervasive online manipulative strategies are unethical to the extent that they limit or hinder someone from being able to manage their own lives according to their own free will decisions. The most serious issue facing society today, in this perspective, is not the exploitation of cognitive biases and vulnerabilities, but rather the fact that many of these exploitative techniques are made to be carried out covertly, giving the hackers influence over how individuals perceive their future tenses (Botes, 2022).

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Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research approach to explore the topic manipulation of people's minds through digitalization, focusing on the ethical considerations versus profit motives. The research involve a total of 10 respondents, consisting of 5 developers and 5 users who were adult and professionals. The respondents were selected from users groups as well as developers employed by organizations engaged in digital technologies, ensuring a diversity of viewpoints. Open ended interview techniques was used for data collection. There were two sets of questions created, one for users and for the developers, which contained 16 questions in the interview schedule. The interview schedule was designed to explore the respondents' experiences, attitudes, and viewpoints about the ethical consequences of manipulating their minds and the roles that profit motives serve in this instance. Data was analyzed using coding and data triangulation analysis method. All data collected from the interviewees were transcribed for validity. Codes were developed and categorized and interpretations were made to give further meaning to the data. These coded data were triangulated for analyses purpose.

Findings and discussion

This study explores the sociological perspectives of manipulation from the general users and the professionals who develops the digital application for the purpose of user friendly application that contributes towards easiness with ongoing life style. However, many organization and developers are intending to gain profit but have limited concern for ethic.

Manipulative mind through digitalization

In this study we explored how developers and user perceive the use of digital application as practicing for profit or ethic. Preferential influence towards persuading the individuals and groups to purchase good is a cognitive balance of manipulating features that are applied in the applications (Izuma and Adolphs, 2013). The results suggest that most user's claims that digital applications have manipulative feature that have also manipulated their emotions and behavior. In this connection user 1 mentions "Yes, I have encountered advertisements that persuade us to purchase products or services. For instance, schools and colleges promise parents to improve their children's grades and easily pass exams if they enroll their children, using emotional appeals to attract them". Manipulative features can be decisive, and information shared to public can have preferential influential ingredients, which allows them to trust not knowing that the information shared are correct. These features are activated by the developers of the application/programme. In the view to reflect the experiences shared by a user, she states;

"I have come across news articles containing manipulative content with a political agenda. Some media sources intentionally present biased information that can misrepresent facts to shape public opinion and influence readers' emotions. I have seen scammers spreading false information, promoting fake donation requests, and using deceptive tactics to gain our personal information or financial advantage".

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Similarly user 2 says

“If YouTube videos count as well, then yes !! I have encountered numerous such videos on YouTube that look like they are presenting facts but in reality are just modification of data in such a way that the viewers might get manipulated easily. Spiritual videos of some fake gurus and some Political commentary news vlogs are the examples”.

In the same connection, user 3 states;

“Yes. Fair and lovely advertisement, Air conditioner advertisement, many more. You can say all contents, ads are made to persuade and manipulate”.

There could be multiple ways to attract and divert peoples mind. Additional content and advertisements can persuade individual towards craving for products through these medium. The sudden arousal of desire to wanting these products can be deceiving to many. This can be the ways to generate profit for the organization. Overlapping of content on applications can also attract peoples mind towards craving for such services or products. Moreover, digitalization have grown far too much that sometimes the content in the application can never be true or correct. This is where breach if ethic can be a major concern, while many of the individuals believe and trust such displays as real but in reality it can be a fake.

Moreover, AI and IT have developed so much in a ways that deep faking have come into practices to manipulate peoples mind. They have been a lot of debate to avoid such deep faking content. However, many people are already manipulated by then. The AI and IT have moved rapidly with multiple designs that somehow defy the intelligent minds of the people. Not all individuals are digitally intelligent, and have knowledge about being manipulated through some unavoidable contents, for them, emotionally captivating can be easy, thus profit can be maximized.

Supporting this view user 4 says;

“I'd say persuade rather than manipulate. I see lots of advertisements and have worked on multiples. The main objective of advertisement is to elicit an emotion and help people solve their problems. But being said that, there will always be black hat players in the scene everywhere. But, me personally, I don't would be easily manipulated by ads or news as I always fact check things and search for cold hard proof before I take any action”.

Similarly user 5 have the opinion who says;

“Yes, news article on online portals manipulates my thought process for example side effects of junk food”.

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The developers are working for the organization or design the application and content for the organizations. In general developers who are working on their own – not for the profit but ill practicing ethical behavior by hacking data base and deep faking portraits. In such circumstances, ethic practices is totally considered to be ignored and this is also illegal. While many are aware of the cyber law crime, it hardly have any action plan unless some secured database is hacked. However, small content that persuade to manipulate emotional behavior of people are ignored by many. This have prioritized the developing agencies to create more of manipulative nature in content to persuade the peoples mind to divert and crave for making decision for wanting such services and products.

Supporting this view, Developer 3 says

“Targeted advertisement I think directly affects the decisions people make. While emotion of people is concerned to attract them with additional content, developers instigate to design such products where people unknowingly put themselves in a position to view such content. The IT have become superficially intelligent to determine the user’s behavioural pattern through the devices they are using and the frequency of their visiting pattern”.

Developer 4 indicates;

“Most common ways that digital technologies or platforms have been designed to influence people's behavior are - they are simple, easy to use, easier to understand, interactive, addictive, targeted contents, etc.”

Moreover, developers feel that ethical practices must be maintained to safeguarding the privacy of users. In this connection, developers 1 states the line between the ethic and profit must also be maintained. Impractical ways of exploiting the users through manipulative pop-ups and advertisement can misguide the user while surfing the particular application. Developers 1 mentions;

“Companies should prioritize user privacy and well-being, implement transparent data practices, and explore alternative revenue models to strike a balance between ethical implications and profitability”.

The clarity of using the application can have various positive consequences to the users. This enables the users to trust the application and can use is without hesitations. In this regard, developers 2 says;

“They should make sure to clarify all the consequences about their products and services that they sell to the end users”.

Internet data are not secured, and this data from the personal sources can be used for any purposes. However the application claims that any information provided by the individuals can be contained and can be compromised. Moreover, some application can seek for the approval of individuals before using the information through multiple choices such as, allow and blocks. However, if an individuals do not give access to the use of personal data, the application may not work or function properly. In some cases, if the

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application is not given access, the application cannot be used for further assistant. This is one way of manipulation that is generated by the application while developing it. Although the application claims the information will not be shared it is however, being compromised. This is how the users are manipulated. Furthermore, it can be trusted that only few information are being compromised and although being manipulated through the use of application some general data can be compromised for which a developer 5 claims that;

“The designed system should take only general data of customers that do not harm in user decision making”.

In any circumstance, whether the application claims to be safe, it may not be safe, somehow or the other, the information can be compromised and this information may not be shared to the users. This is how the users through the digital technologies are being manipulated. More sophisticated application are being developed and more of modern devices are required to use the application. In other ways, a developers of an application are also manipulating the users/individuals to acquire the modern devices. Moreover, while understanding the usages of applications with the technologies both the manufacturer of the modern devices and the developers have the role of manipulating the users if they are to be kept consistent with the digitalized era. Either ways it can also be understood that users are always being manipulated and this manipulative behavioural pattern persuade the user/individuals to acquire a new device and the use of modern applications facilities that is specifically designed to be used by the end users who so ever.

Ethic versus profit

Ethic versus profit is a long debate in managerial implications. Managerial implications can create stress whether to incline towards profit or towards applying an ethical consideration (Rajbhandari and Jans, 2023). This stress through the implications of managerial objectives more significantly addresses towards gaining profit. Although many organizations claims to be practicing ethical behavioural pattern for the benefit of individuals who uses the device and application are just claiming to win the trust of users. In practicality, all organization and application have the manipulative features to attract users for which profit can be maximized. The presence of mindfulness must be transformed to the users. Developer 1 states;

“Companies and developers vary in their awareness of the consequences of design decisions on users, but there is increasing recognition and action being taken to prioritize user well-being through ethical design practices. However, some may still prioritize engagement and profitability over user welfare”.

In the same line developer 4 also mentions;

“Companies should always use costumer's personal information ethically or safely and protect it from unauthorized and illegal use and also from misuse of the information. Companies can use customer's information for targeted advertising while making profit but the information should be regulated with the algorithms within the company only and it should not manipulate the data and sell to partner or others companies for any of the business or personal use. Company should always take responsibility

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to take care of their customer's information and should always use that information properly and ethically”.

Although, government in some countries have implied a cyber law for unethical behavior, there are still few elements involved in hacking into personal data. This could be possible with a modern device or through the use of installed application in their devices. In recent years, manipulation are being converted into ethical practices by having the default application already installed in the device where updates are regularly available. Some of the application installed are permanent and may not be uninstalled or disabled. Technically, the unused application can be disabled, most users are not technologically intelligent and some may not have time to look into details of what the applications offers.

While managerial implicative approaches are applied in any organization, the motive to profit maximization cannot be ignored. However, deceiving users through the modern devices and forcibly implying to use the application can also be controlled to some extent that trust is developed.

Developer 4 mentions;

“Growing uses of artificial intelligence and machine learning have made development of digitization in human life to the next level. AI can do users work very fast and repeatedly in the same speed. AI can understand the behavior of user and acts like a friend. Though human can use ethics for work but AI can be unethical if it fails or altered it's programs. It can kill many life”.

In the same line, developer 5 says

“Growing AI can change people jobs and there lifestyles. AI will make people mind dull and unproductive”.

Profit maximization policy of an organization can have multiple goals. This could be either a personal goal or the organizational goal. In between a thin line of personal goal and organizational goal, a personal goal can be very intense. Rajbhandari (2011) illustrate a FOSS model (Focus, Optimistic, Striving and Smile) to explain the intentions of an organizational leader to achieving personal goal or to maintain organizational goal. While organizational goal is reflects towards welfare and well-being of employees and users with the intention by applying Social Corporate responsibility (CSR), however, personal goal deflects the intention of an organizational leaders towards achieving for themselves. Developer 2 states;

“Yes. Because they have not built the applications for helping the poor ones. The founders are doing and building to make billions so that they can ride Lamborghini”.

In the same vein, developer 3 mentions;

“Definitely. The only purpose for designing application for most of the cases is to make a profit. Because running an application requires a lot of resources”.

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While discussing on drawing a thin line between ethics versus profit, it is certain that most organization are working to generate a profitable business. For this ethic can be compromised. To support this view, user 1 states;

“Yes, companies are developing the applications with the intention of making profit. there is huge competition in market in innovative development field. They monetizes the user data, enable subscription mode,etc. for making profit”.

In the same connection to support the views user 3 mentions;

“Yes, companies develop applications to make a profit. They do so to sustain their business, achieve a return on investment, meet market demand, outperform competitors, utilize monetization models, and fulfill obligations to investors and stakeholders”.

Agreeing the views of the statement profit can be the primary motives of an organization before the ethical practices, user 4 also mentions;

“Why would they create applications? If not for creating profit? Unless they're a heavily funded organization that can survive without profit, every application/software is designed to create profit, may the profit be in short term or longer term in others”.

User 5 have the same opinion to express for which she states;

“Yes, majority of the corporates exist to generate profit”.

There are multiple ways to manipulate users, this manipulative features in an application or in any modern devices forcibly attract the user to unknowingly use the program. Would this be unethical to users but it can be a profit maximization strategy for the organization. A developers can have a major role in applying this strategies by installing a bug program that enables the users to accept the usability. The consequences can be different. In this connection, user 2 supports his view by stating his experiences, he says;

“Advertisement can be one example, they first make us insecure about ourselves just to make us buy their product. Yes, that one time when I was searching for online course details and the next day I got call from them if I want to register for course (very terrifying and confusing at the same time)”.

The program engraved into an application activates while online and the program can initiates to direct the link towards another platform, which users are forcibly linked to a different platform despite their unwillingness. Some application are designed in such a manner that it can be almost impossible for the users to end the program. The skip and stop button are almost invisible or not present in the running application.

Organization today are craving for success in a competitive world. This is also due to rapid growth in modernization and technological innovation. General people are left with multiple choices of products and services. Earlier manipulation was physically created by pattern of colourful design, however, clever people could easily avoid such attractions. In this modernization era, manipulation are seen observantly in service sectors, moreover these manipulation in service sector have also connected with internet technology and artificial intelligence both in physical products and in computerized programmed application. Either ways this manipulative simulation is forcibly designed to attract consumers.

Towards gaining competitive advantage and absolute advantage in this digitalization era can be difficult. This is because of frequent development in technology through new innovation in AI and technology, whether it be the computerized application towards serving the purpose of consumer or in general.

Nevertheless, the competitive advantage is gained by the organization by manipulating the peoples mind by either attracting to involve into the application knowingly or unknowingly. This can be dangerous for people while most data could be leaked and the security of breach with data and social personal security is publicly shared.

Ethic and profit, does it go along together? While ethic is maintain, sacrifices in profit margin have to be compromised while organization concentrate in profit, ethic have to be compromised. However, most organization and developers do not want to compromise profit with ethic. The norms of managerial practices have diverted into profit making for the entrepreneurs while on the other hand, general people using the application demand for ethic. A thin line that boarder the relationship between ethic and profit may be erased and this can be a concern for all.

In recent days, entrepreneurial development also have taken a different shapes. Entrepreneurs are innovators and the developers considers themselves as an innovators since they are the one who innovate new digitalized application. This can be considered correct with some few stance of entrepreneurial definition, however, entrepreneurs are also visionary who creates an environment for social welfare, wellness and well-being. These aspects are ignored by the developers and the organization who initiates to develop new application that basically focuses on the organizational products forcing the individuals/people to get involved. This is where the thin line boarder is being erased. Moreover, the developers and the organizations claiming to becoming an entrepreneurial role are taking up a role of a managerial and administrative activities rather than becoming a socially obliged to people using the application.

Conclusively, Manipulation of peoples mind through digitalization is almost existence in every devices and application that the user prefer to use. However, it is also evident that some of the application are programmed by default, which can also instigate the user's to use it while making a purchase of modern technological equipped devices. Moreover, technological devices in recent development, either it be google home, alexa, apple home kit or any other technologically equipped devices through internet connection can have a features engraved to manipulative nature. This is due to the sophisticated use of the modern devices which manipulative the people's minds and is developed with an intention of profit maximization objectives by an organization.

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Somehow, it is also evident that most organizations and developers are inclined towards maximization of profit where, ethics versus profit can collide. Nevertheless, the choices are made for profit maximization while considering ethics are found to be minimal. The results also suggest that manipulation of people's mind cannot be made free for the sake of organizational existence for a longer run and to compete with rival organizations or developers. The strategies for manipulation of people's mind are evident and is made possible through the use of technological intelligence or AI technologies. These programmed technologies are making the users dependable to rely on their applications and program. The results also suggest that both organizations and developers have equal possibilities to develop an AI to manipulate the people's mind either knowingly or unknowingly and almost all users' falls under the manipulations streamline. This is also because the dependency of technology has created the social and professional environment to knot tightly. However, would they be any escape from the AI and digitalization culture in this or coming era? Would digitalization be free from manipulative features? And will ethics be given a first priority over the profit maximization in near future, while most organization speaks about becoming socially responsible towards the community?

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